

Studies on the Reactions of Oxohalomolybdates(V)

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The isolation and study of the new salt $(\text{CpyH})_2[\text{MoOBr}_5]$ and its derivatives $[\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_3\text{Br}_4\text{Cpy}_2]$ and $[\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_4\text{Br}_2\text{Cpy}_2]$ are reported. It is interesting to note that although both the ring-nitrogen and that in—CN group function as donor sites, only one of these is appreciably basic and is subsequently protonated to yield the salt $(\text{CpyH})_2[\text{MoOBr}_5]$. These compounds have been studied by analytical and other physicochemical methods.

It has been previously observed by Saha and his coworkers¹ that the products of reactions of oxohalomolybdates (V) both in aqueous and nonaqueous media mainly depend on the nature of halogen X and the organic base R in $\text{RH}_2[\text{MoOX}_5]$. While studying the catalytic effect of quinquevalent molybdenum in the hydrolysis of 2, cyanopyridine it was firstly observed by Saha and Mandal² that this organic base serves as a potential bidentate ligand for quinquevalent molybdenum. Detail investigations by us have established the specificity of 2Cpy as a potential bidentate ligand to molybdenum in quinquevalent state. Even trivalent iron in high spin state having close analogy with MoO^{5+} ion³ does not react with 2,cyanopyridine.

Experimental

All reagents used were of A.R. grade.

Analysis

Molybdenum and bromine were estimated gravimetrically as molybdenum trioxide and silver bromide, and nitrogen by Dumas' method. Oxidation state of the metal was determined by ceric sulphate method.

Preparation

2-cyanopyridinium Oxopentabromomolybdate(V)
 $(\text{CpyH})_2[\text{MoOBr}_5]$.

About 1 g molybdenum trioxide was gently boiled with 10 ml of 48% hydrobromic acid and was almost evaporated to dryness. A fresh amount of 10 ml hydrobromic acid was added and the operation repeated. The residue was taken up with 10 ml of the same acid. To this solution was added 2 ml of 2-cyanopyridine acidified with hydrobromic acid with stirring in cold. The mixture was stirred and cooled in freezing mixture and hydrobromic acid gas was passed till the golden yellow crystalline solid appeared. This was filtered, washed with hydrobromic acid and was dried in vacuum desiccator over solid KOH. Yield 3.5 g.

Found Mo, 12.78% ; Br, 55.88% ; N, 7.89%.

Calc. for $(\text{CpyH})_2[\text{MoOBr}_5]$ Mo, 13.29% ; Br, 55.4% and N, 7.7%. Oxidation state of the metal was found to be 4.99.

Oxo-μ-oxodibromo (2-cyanopyridine) molybdenum(V)
 $[\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_3\text{Br}_4\text{Cpy}_2]$.

About 1 g of 2-cyanopyridine oxopentabromomolybdate (V) was boiled with 15 ml of dehydrated ethanol when a deep violet solution was obtained. To the cooled solution ether was added and stirred continuously when deep violet solid separated out. It was filtered through sintered gooch crucible and dried in a vacuum desiccator. Yield 0.8 g.

Found. Mo, 24.92% ; Br, 41.08% ; N, 7.33%. Calc. for $[\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_3\text{Br}_4\text{Cpy}_2]$ Mo, 25% ; Br, 41.66% and N, 7.29%. Oxidation state of the metal was found to be 5.01.

Oxo-μ-dioxobromo (2-cyanopyridine) molybdenum (V)
 $[\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_4\text{Br}_2\text{Cpy}_2]$.

About 1 g of 2-cyanopyridine oxopentabromomolybdate(V) was boiled with 20 ml water with constant stirring when a yellow solid separated out. The product was filtered, washed with cold water and dried in a vacuum desiccator. Yield 0.6 g.

Found. Mo, 31.03% ; Br, 24.94% ; N, 8.20%. Calc. for $[\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_4\text{Br}_2\text{Cpy}_2]$ Mo, 30.76% ; Br, 25.64% ; N, 8.97%. Oxidation state of the metal was found to be 5.06.

Magnetic susceptibility measurements

The magnetic susceptibility of the compounds were measured in Gouy balance using a field strength of 8500 gauss. The values of magnetic moments were calculated using the formula $\mu_{\text{eff}} = 2.839 (\chi'_M)^{\frac{1}{2}}$ where χ'_M is the molar susceptibility after

diamagnetic correction. The μ_{eff} value of $(\text{CpyH})_2[\text{MoOBr}_5]$ is 1.798 (B.M.) at 29° confirming the presence of MoO^{5+} unit in the compound with d^1 configuration of Mo whereas the μ_{eff} value of $[\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_3\text{Br}_4\text{Cpy}_2]$ and $[\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_4\text{Br}_2\text{Cpy}_2]$ are found to be 1.19 and .646 (B.M.) at 31° and 30° respectively, which indicate the presence of oxobridges in the compounds.

I. R. spectra

I. R. spectra of the compounds were recorded in Perkin Elmer I. R. Spectrophotometer using KBr plates. All the three compounds show a strong

Fig. 1. Electronic spectra of $(\text{CpyH})_2[\text{MoOBr}_5]$ in acetonitrile.

TABLE 1. ELECTRONIC SPECTRA IN ACETONITRILE

Compound	λ_{max} ($m\mu$)	$\nu(\text{cm}^{-1} \times 10^{-3})$	Molar extinction coefficient	Possible assignment
$(\text{CpyH})_2[\text{MoOBr}_5]$	690	14.5	14	${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2E$ (I)
	475	21.05	380	${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2B_1$
	402	24.88	1400	${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2E$ (II)
	335	29.85	500	${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2B_2$ (I)
	264	37.87	6700	${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2B_2$ (II)
	225	44.44	9100	${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2E$ (III)

absorption band in the region $945\text{--}975\text{ cm}^{-1}$ which is characteristic of Mo(V)=O stretching vibration.

Electronic spectra

The electronic spectra of the salt 2-cyanopyridinium oxopentabromomolybdate (V) were recorded in Hilger UVISPEK using acetonitrile as solvent. Reflectance spectra were taken for two binuclear complexes $[\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_3\text{Br}_4\text{Cpy}_2]$ and $[\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_4\text{Br}_2\text{Cpy}_2]$ in paraffin base. The results are plotted in figs 1 and 2 and their assignments are given in table 1 and 2.

Fig. 2. Reflectance spectra of I. $\text{MO}_2\text{O}_4\text{Br}_2\text{Cpy}_2$, II. $\text{MO}_2\text{O}_3\text{Br}_4\text{Cpy}_2$

TABLE-2 REFLECTANCE SPECTRA

Compound	λ_{max} ($m\mu$)	$\nu(\text{cm}^{-1} \times 10^{-3})$	Inten- sity	Assignments
$[\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_3\text{Br}_4\text{Cpy}_2]$	600	16.66	w	$d \quad d \quad d$ $x^2-y^2 \rightarrow xz \quad yz$
	420	23.81	s	$d \quad d$ $x^2-y^2 \rightarrow xy$
	378	26.45	w	$\pi \rightarrow d$ x^2-y^2
	800	12.5	w	$\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$
$[\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_4\text{Br}_2\text{Cpy}_2]$	610	16.4	w	$d \quad d \quad d$ $x^2-y^2 \rightarrow xz \quad yz$
	442	22.6	m	$d \quad d$ $x^2-y^2 \rightarrow xy$
	392	25.51	m	$\pi \rightarrow d$ x^2-y^2

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